

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BAYU****FIRST NAME: TEWODROS****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 365 on Windows 10)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The EUCLID course on International Academic Writing ACA-401 introduces the student with the fundamentals of international academic writing used at graduate-level studies, most specifically at the Ph.D. level. It describes in detail the requirements, skills, and techniques of writing academic papers in an international context so that student's writing skills are on the level required.

EUCLID expects a higher level of excellence and perfection at this level. Hence, one has to be detailed, disciplined, and dedicate adequate time to become a perfect writer. Therefore, as a non-native speaker of the English language, I carefully reviewed the reading material and the video lessons with corresponding sources available online so that I perfectly apply the knowledge and skills acquired from the course and meet the requirements.

I found the topics covered in the coursepack relevant to the study of diplomacy and international affairs and my day to day work. Like any other field of study, both students and practitioners of diplomacy and international affairs should be able to write perfectly and correctly. A combination of writing skills, tools, and techniques presented in the coursepack allowed me to question my writing skills and revisit my styles. More than ever, I am now very careful about grammatical correctness, use of punctuation marks, logical flow, coherence, citations, rules of styles, and format. I will be referring to the coursepack every time I write response papers or other assignments that involve writing.

2) PERIOD 1 – THE COURSE PACK

The course pack has 83 pages and covers topics such as the basics of essay writing, qualities of an excellent paper, plagiarism, the rules of thumb for writing papers, American vs. British English, the Chicago-Turabian style which I will be using in my field of study and other styles applicable to other fields of studies. Common grammatical mistakes, punctuations, and Latin abbreviations used in writing were also among the topics covered. In addition to the EUCLID templates for response papers and samples of corrected papers, a clear and step by step video lesson accompanies the coursepack which helped me a lot to practice and interact with the EUCLID templates, formats, and rule of styles.

I had some writing experience and some of the topics covered in the coursepack sound somehow familiar from my graduate and undergraduate studies. But I have forgotten most of them such as the use of punctuation, common grammatical mistakes in writing essays, and the rule of styles. However, the Turabian style and Zotero are completely new to me. Hence, I convinced myself to read carefully and practice frequently so that my writings are perfect, correct, and meet the EUCLID standards.

Qualities of good academic essay and the steps that need to be followed are presented in very good detail (EUCLID 2019, 2–4) and I learned that one needs to have a combination of skills, arts, tools, and techniques to be a very good writer. I am particularly pleased to read creative thinking and critical thinking skills (EUCLID 2019, 3) as essential writing skills. While the former broadens the writer's ideas, the later encourages to narrow the focus of the idea and build it with relevant arguments. During my undergraduate studies, my professors, most of whom are specialized in Philosophical studies, use the level of critical and creative thinking skills as an evaluation criterion. On the other hand, as a former Journalist, I used to complete journalistic stories and feature articles within a few hours or days to meet deadlines. But I knew my writings were not perfect even then, and this coursepack reminded me of my mistakes.

It is now clear to me that academic essays, papers, etc. are not the same – thinking should be accompanied by art, skills, and proficiency in writing. Moreover, careful planning, proper formatting, logical coherence, connection, and flow of ideas to meet the qualities of a good essay (EUCLID 2019, 4–7). From the introduction to the body and then the conclusion, the right rule of styles, formats, punctuations, references, and citations should be applied. Most of all, plagiarism should be avoided by all means, a topic presented in the course pack in very good detail.

I read the section on plagiarism with particular interest because my academic writing experience is limited to writing the graduate and undergraduate papers. While I am aware that it is wrong, unethical, and pose a serious academic offense (EUCLID 2019, 12), when and how to paraphrase remained a challenge to me until I read the paraphrasing section (EUCLID 2019, 29). I also learned that EUCLID pays particular attention to the dangers of plagiarism and provided adequate examples of how to apply various types of citations. How to quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source, and copy-pasting from the internet are some of the topics I

understood well. The most common forms of plagiarism are presented in detail. To avoid this serious academic offense, EUCLID strictly advises students to use direct quotations which indeed are useful and practical. Similarly, the overuse of citations and alternative techniques and examples of paraphrasing is elaborated so that overuse of citations does not affect the originality of the writing (EUCLID 2019, 29–35).

Even though I have the interest, I was particularly not exposed to the use of any rule of style. I was using Microsoft Word to insert references, footnotes, endnotes, etc. manually, which was a tedious task. The course pack has exposed me to different rules of styles. I learned that I will be using the Chicago-Turabian rule of style for my EUCLID papers (EUCLID 2019, 83). I am also introduced to the APA (American Psychological Association) style, which will also be useful in my future work (EUCLID 2019, 66). These particular lessons made me enthusiastic to master the Zotero, Grammarly, and other applicable software tools which will significantly improve my efficiency and proficiency in applying the rule of styles and correct use of the English language. For now, Zotero is having issues to synchronize with my chrome browser and Microsoft Word - I had to review other online sources to ensure that my office package and browser is compatible with Zotero.

I read the section on American and British English with particular interest and enthusiasm. Although I am familiar with some of the punctuations and common mistakes discussed under 'LIT-101 REVIEW' (EUCLID 2019, 51–53), I was not aware that British and American English have differences as such. Hence, paying due attention to formal and informal communication, for example, will have huge importance to the study of diplomacy and international affairs. Formal writing should be correct, detailed, and should be perfect. For example, I was not paying attention to the proper use of business and social letters, the use of numerals, "that" and "which", and "its" and "it's". As a non-native speaker of the English language, (EUCLID 2019, 53–59), this helped me to differentiate the formal from the informal and learned when to apply periods, commas, and quotation marks. Words, concepts, and expressions mean could lead to misunderstanding and miscommunication, another important lesson for the study of diplomacy and international affairs.

The sample corrected papers (EUCLID 2019, 60) is another ideal example for me to understand the essential etiquettes, styles, and formats. The comments inserted in 'bold' are very helpful to understand the power of the second eye in reviewing essays. However, I found the format, template, and rule of style different from the EUCLID template presented for response papers – a mix of formats and styles is applied. Instead of intext reference style, footnotes are applied (EUCLID 2019, 64). I was also wondering as to why the entire coursepack is missing any table of content, headings, or standard footnote or endnote references.

In both formal and informal writings, I tend to avoid the use of abbreviations because the meaning and interpretations sometimes confuse me. I was also worried that I could easily be misunderstood and did not know if this could be acceptable either in formal or informal settings. But now at least I know what would be acceptable to abbreviate in written communication. The details on common abbreviations presented under the Chicago

style and usage clarified this and improved my confidence (EUCLID 2019, 66). The plausible reasons behind the use of margins, fonts, indents, justification, and spacing are also clarified with good examples (EUCLID 2019, 71) and I am ready to use them in my response papers or other works. Moreover, the Chicago endnotes and footnotes (EUCLID 2019, 75) provide sufficient examples as to how Books, Journals, Magazines, Newspapers, Articles, conference papers, Ph.D. dissertations, webpage, and other works should be cited. With the help of Zotero, I am confident that I will be using these rules of style in my response papers, major papers, or others in my field of study. Moreover, I find this extremely important in my day to day work.

3) CONCLUSION

Overall, I find the coursepack interesting and useful for students of diplomacy and international affairs. I read it with enthusiasm to gain new and/or additional knowledge and skills that I would apply in my future work. Hence, I have already started to apply the learning in my day to day work which involves the regular interaction with research consultants on project assessment studies, research studies, and other regular reports. To some extent, this response paper itself is written based on the knowledge and skills gained from the coursepack. I am hopeful that others will also find the contents relevant to their study and field of work.

I found the course pack very practical and full of details and illustrative examples. It has improved my writing and reading skills and would help me to make contributions to my area of study. In addition to creative and critical thinking skills, I very much believe that the combination of skills, tools, and techniques presented in the coursepack and video lessons will make me a good writer who perfectly apply the EUCLID rule of style, formats, templates, and other details. Moreover, I am sure that I will be revising various sections of the coursepack every time I write response papers and/or major papers in the future.

There is no doubt that the contents are carefully organized and very rich in detail. But I would suggest restructuring the sequence of the different topics so that they have a logical flow. While those related to writing skills, essay writing, grammar, punctuation could be arranged in one section, those related to the rule of style, referencing, and Zotero could be presented in another subsequent section so that students could easily use the coursepack in their future work. The section on plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 42), which I found extremely important, could also be presented in Microsoft Word format within a few pages instead of PowerPoint presentation form so that concepts are condensed and presented in proper written format. The chosen format is also not uniform across all pages and does not strictly follow the EUCLID format and style. In some instances, citations were omitted. But I am finally satisfied to see the latest version of the same coursepack, entitled 'ACA401/ACA-401D'(Cleenewerck and Gulma 2019). It is a good example of how the course reading material should be organized so that students like me could easily use it as a reference in future work.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University. 2nd edition.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.